

AN APPROACH TO CAPITAL COMPETENCES FOOTPRINTS: A CASE STUDY FROM NORTHERN PORTUGAL

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This communication discusses the spatial impact of anthropogenic emissions and infrastructure development in Arcos de Valdevez, Portugal, in connection with the social composition of its parishes. By investigating air quality, nightlight radiance, building ages, and road infrastructures, the research highlights the relationship between physical traces and the economic and cultural characteristics of residents. Using satellite imagery, open-access data, and the 2021 Portuguese census, a Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and Mixed Classification (MC) were applied to identify multidimensional spatial patterns. The results introduce the concept of "emplaced capital footprints," which refers to the objectification of social competences within physical spaces. This approach emphasizes how infrastructure and emissions are linked to social dynamics, revealing the spatial manifestation of social class strivings, land-use changes, and local industries. The analysis includes the consideration of roads, buildings, electric nightlight and key air pollutants—PM2.5, PM10, NO2, SO2, CO, O3, and NH3— tracked via satellite, and collective open access databases, framing them as markers of embedded capital competences rather than purely environmental concerns. Ultimately, the study offers an exploratory approach to how socio-economic dynamics are substantially inscribed in the landscape, shaping both physical and social space.